

A Study of Employee Motivation in Organization

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ABSTRACT

Employee Motivation is the key factor to help up the capacity of an association. In the globalization stage, each organization needs to continue itself in a furiously focused market. Representatives are the fundamental elements to show the business objectives into the real world. Subsequently, in the present world each association attempts to deal with its human asset office to keep its representatives inspired. In that specific circumstance, some of the administration speculations have been rehearsing by them. Business work or their presentation in the market can be assessed by surveying the degree of inspiration of representatives. Inspiration can assume a lead job to get the expert achievement in each budgetary year in a less exertion way.

While trying to find what inspires representatives, representative inspiration inquire about papers report that what spurs laborers today is fundamentally connected to the qualities and objectives of the person. Starting in the 1970's, it appears that there was a sensational move in the qualities and needs of the ordinary laborer. As individuals turned out to be progressively taught and the economy saw a sharp decay of the Protestant hard working attitudes, what representatives needed from their managers changed also.

Keywords-- Motivation, Employee Motivation, Rewarding, Drives and Needs

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee retention is one of the most significant factors in the field of human asset the board. Capable and faithful employees are a base for effective organizations, and hence holding them is essential. Preparing new workers is tedious and requires more assets, in this way the more drawn out a representative remains with the organization, the better it is for the association.

II. MOTIVATION

Motivation is a significant factor that urges people to give their best execution and help in arriving at big business objectives. Solid positive inspiration will empower the expanded yield of workers yet a negative inspiration will decrease their exhibition. A key component in work force the executives is motivation.

Types of Motivation-

1. Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation is a type of motivation in which an individual is being motivated by internal desires. For example, let's say an individual named Bob has define himself an objective to start shedding pounds and getting more beneficial. How about we likewise envision that Bob's motivation to seek after this way of wellness and wellbeing is to improve his wellbeing in general and feel more joyful

with his appearance. Since Bob's craving to change originates from inside, his inspiration is intrinsic.

2. Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is a type of motivation in which an individual is being motivated by external desires.

Instead of being inspired by the need to look better and feel more beneficial, suppose that Bob was feeling pressure from his significant other to thin down and improve his physical make-up with the goal that she would be more pulled in to him. Since this weight originates all things considered this is an example of extrinsic motivation.

3. Positive Motivation

In real sense, motivation means positive motivation. Positive motivation initiates individuals to do work in the most ideal way and to improve their presentation. Under this better offices and prizes are accommodated their better execution. Such rewards and offices might be money related and non-monetary.

4. Negative Motivation

Negative motivation aims at controlling the negative endeavors of the work and tries to make a feeling of dread for the laborer, which he needs to languish over absence of good execution. It depends on the idea that if a laborer flops in accomplishing the ideal outcomes, he ought to be rebuffed.

Minor Forms of Motivation

All types of motivation are going to fall into one of the two categories above. Now that we've covered these motivational types and provided you with some examples, here are minor forms of motivation that are capable of making a big impact in your life!

5. Reward-Based Motivation or Incentive Motivation

Incentive motivation or reward-based motivation is a type of motivation that is utilized when you or others know that they will be a reward once a certain goal is achieved. Since there will be something to anticipate toward the finish of an errand, individuals will regularly turn out to be increasingly resolved to oversee the undertaking with the goal that they can get whatever it is that has been guaranteed. The better the prize, the more grounded the inspiration will be !

6. Fear-Based Motivation

The word "fear" carries a heavy negative meaning but when it comes to motivation, this is not necessarily the case. Anyone who is big on goal-setting and achievement knows that accountability plays a huge role in following through on goals.

At the point when you become responsible either to somebody you care about or to the overall population, you make an inspiration for yourself that is established in the dread of disappointment. This dread encourages you to do your vision with the goal that you don't bomb before the individuals who know about your objective. Dread based inspiration is incredibly ground-breaking as long as the feelings of dread is sufficiently able to keep you from stopping.

7. Achievement-Based Motivation

Titles, positions, and roles throughout jobs and other areas of our lives are very important to us. Those who are constantly driven to acquire these positions and earn titles for themselves are typically dealing with achievement-based motivation.

Theories used for the Employee Motivation for Improving Business Operation

Motivational factor for the employees to improve the business operation can be supported by some important theories of management field; those theories are the Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory, Herzberg's Two-factor theory, Expectancy theory and McGregor's X and Y theory.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Psychologist Abraham Maslow portrayed that in order to jump on the next level of psychological development, a person needs to satisfy himself or herself in all perspective, from where at present they existing, The characteristics of human life became satisfied when they can avail the psychological, safety, love, esteem and self-actualization process in their life span. Many organizations followed this theory to keep motivated their employees.

Diagram of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Source: Anderson, 2014)

Expectancy Theory

The expectancy theory proposes that employees' behavior depends over the outcome the action. It suggests the aspects that when employees want hike in their salary increment they start working in longer hours. In this theory there have three main factors that are the expectancy, instrumentality and valence. In a workplace this theory can be executed by the authority, by giving reward to the employees for their good performance.

Diagram of Expectancy theory (Source: Datuk Dr. Mahamad Zubir bin Seeht Saad 2018)

Herzberg two Factor Theory

a) **Motivator factors:** The factors such like salary increment, good working environment motivate workers.
 b) **Hygiene factors:** Those factors which can de-motivate the employees, such as company policies, salary deduction, Unhealthy relationship with managers and coworkers.

Diagrams of Herzberg two factor theory Source: Datuk Dr. Mahamad Zubir bin Seeht Saad 2018

Values and Employee Motivation

Today, it seems that many of these values and needs have changed and as a result, the values of today's employee focus on self and emphasize characteristics that lead to self-development and self-fulfillment. These include the following:

- Little loyalty or commitment to an organization.
- A need for recognition of one's accomplishments.
- Little concern with job security and stability.
- Leisure considered more important than work.
- Desire for work that is challenging, that provides opportunities for personal growth and development, and that calls for creativity.
- Desire to participate in decisions that affect one's job.
- A stronger identification with one's personal role in all facets of life rather than with one's work role.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Motivation

Shultz and Shultz continue by noting that the values and needs of the individual when met translate into job satisfaction and "a high level of job satisfaction is directly related to positive behavior on the job, specifically to high performance, low turnover, and low absenteeism". Employee motivation research papers further this point by stating that, "For any effective work to occur, there must be a certain amount of consensus on basic values". Therefore it is important to select individuals whose values and goals match those of the organization. This will ultimately produce satisfied employees, a productive workforce and hence a more successful organization.

There are various factors motivating an employee, which determine what is the most valuable, important to the employee. As a rule, this is not one factor, but several, and together they make up a map or a set of motivators of the employee. These factors are divided into external and internal.

Internal factors are:

- Self-actualization
- Creativity
- Self-affirmation
- Conviction
- Curiosity
- Health
- Personal growth
- The need for communication

External factors of motivation are:

- Money
- Careers
- Status
- Prestige
- Ability to travel

Moreover, the thought processes of human conduct are distinctive in nature and the sky is the limit from there: they

can be sure (to get, hold) or negative (to dispose of, to maintain a strategic distance from). Along these lines, the constructive outer thought process is a reward that an individual can get for good work, and negative can be discipline for its inability to agree; positive inward rationale is love for an occupation, in which the worker is locked in, and the negative can be its normal nature, coming about, actually, in the goal to dispose of it.

III. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To Evaluate the Effects of Motivation and satisfaction at workplace.
2. To Identify the Approaches used to Motivate Employees.
3. To Identify the Employee participation in decision making

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

The aim of the research was to find ways how to motivate the employees at Mind Science India Pvt. Limited. Considering the fact that Mind Science has more than 200 employees, and 100 it was reasonable to use the qualitative research methods instead of the quantitative, which suits more researches with large amounts of responses. The interview is one of the qualitative research methods and it can be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured. The structured interviews usually produce quantitative data, and with the unstructured interview the purpose is to gain more of observational data. Therefore, a semi-structured interview fit to the purpose of the research the best. The semi-structured interview usually contains predetermined open-ended questions, and additionally other questions that are originated during the interview.

V. DATA COLLECTION

The interviews were implemented during three different days within a period of one week. The schedules for the interviews were planned together with the manager in order that there would be multiple interviews in one day, and the employees wouldn't have to use their free time for it. Therefore, the interviews were supposed to take place during a certain part of a day when most employees were working at the same time.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS

Q1. What is your satisfaction level at workplace..?

Q2. Following motivational factors used in the organisation..?

Q3. Opinion regarding participation in decision making..?

Q4. Type of approaches motivates you more?

Q5. Factors , which decrease the motivation level at work place..?

Interpretation

- Some employee says that they are motivated only if there is money elements involved.

- Some says non monetary rewards, benefits act as a positive force and increases the job performance.
- And some say non monetary benefits

VII. CONCLUSION

Motivation is an important aspect within any organization and consequently ought to be overseen appropriately if high profitability in the association is normal. Authoritative administrators should in this manner target impacting positive representative directs through inspiring them to guarantee that they submit their endeavors towards hierarchical achievement. In any case, directors should begin by adjusting representative needs with authoritative targets if such duty is normal. Certain inspirational speculations can assume a significant job in directing authoritative administrators through the representative inspiration process. This would guarantee that they receive compelling persuasive methodologies that can tolerate positive outcomes.

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